

Supplemental Table 5 (S5)

Proportional prevalence of *T. cruzi* lineages/all genotyped specimens in mammal taxa; values for total and single infections for TcI and TcVI and mixed TcI+TcVI are included. [confidence interval > 95%, CI]. Bonferroni adjusted significance for χ^2 frequencies in bold: greater than expected * = $p < 0.01$; ** = $p < 0.001$; lower † = $p < 0.01$; †† = $p < 0.001$.

	Single TcI % (N) [CI]	Total TcI % (N) [CI]	Single TcVI % (N) [CI]	Total TcVI % (N) [CI]	TcI + TcVI % (N) [CI]	TcII % (N) [CI]
Primates	53.3 (15) [28.1 - 78.6]	73.3[†] (15) [50.9 - 95.7]	26.7** (15) [4.3 - 49.1]	46.7 (15) [21.4 - 71.9]	20.0 (15) [0.0 - 40.2]	0.0 (15)
Chiroptera	88.7** (62) [80.8 - 96.6]	98.4 (62) [95.3 - 100.0]	1.6 (62) [0.0 - 4.7]	11.3^{††} (62) [8.8 - 13.8]	9.8[†] (62) [2.3 - 17.0]	0.0 (62)
Didelphimorphia	80.0 (5) [44.9 - 100.0]	100.0 (5)	100.0 (5)	20.0 (5) [0.0 - 55.1]	20.0 (5) [0.0 - 55.1]	0.0 (5)
Rodentia	56.7 (30) [38.9 - 74.4]	90.0 (30) [79.3 - 100.0]	6.7 (30) [0.0 - 15.6]	40.0 (30) [22.5 - 57.5]	33.3 (30) [16.5 - 50.2]	3.3 (30) [0.0 - 20.2]
Carnivora (wildlife)	100.0 (2)	100.0 (2)	0.0 (2)	0.0 (2)	0.0 (2)	0.0 (2)
Carnivora (companion)	27.3[†] (11) [0.9 - 53.6]	90.9 (11) [66.3 - 100.0]	9.1 (11) [0.0 - 26.1]	72.7* (11) [46.4 - 99.1]	63.6* (11) [35.2 - 92.1]	0.0 (11)
Artiodactyla	40.0 (15) [15.2 - 64.8]	93.3 (15) [80.7 - 100.0]	6.7 (15) [0.0 - 19.3]	60.0 (15) [35.2 - 84.8]	53.3* (15) [28.1 - 78.6]	0.0 (15)
Perissodactyla	100.0 (1)	100.0 (1)	0.0 (1)	0.0 (1)	0.0 (1)	0.0 (1)
All mammals	68.1 (141) [60.4 - 75.8]	92.9 (141) [88.7 - 97.1]	6.4 (141) [2.3 - 10.4]	31.2 (141) [23.6 - 38.9]	25.0 (141) [17.7 - 32.0]	0.7 (141) [0.0 - 7.8]